

Lagrangian Theory from Special Relativity?

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Lagrangian theory was developed as a mathematical approach to obtaining $F=dp/dt$. As a result, nonrelativistically it is directly associated with $F=dp/dt$. It is well-known that for a free particle, the Lagrangian is $-m_0 \sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. Here we suggest that one may develop Lagrange theory directly from special relativity and specifically find $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ from $F=dp/dt$. As a result, $F=dp/dt$ is still a key equation in special relativity and the variational approach used in the Lagrange method is really designed to obtain the d/dt acting on p . We show that the explicit form $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ follows from $F=dp/dt$ and it is this form which allows the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ to be written as: $\int L dt$ where $L=-E+px$. The explicit form of $g(v)$ then leads to $dL/dv = p$. The next step is to recover d/dt acting on p which occurs if one introduces a variational approach in order to use integration by parts. $dL/dv \delta x/dt$ allows one, through integration by parts, to bring over $-d/dt$ acting on p such that δx remains. In other words, special relativity and $F=dp/dt$ yield $g(v)=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and one may use a Lorentz invariant, which when varied on x,t (the path) allows one to recover $F=dp/dt$.

Classical Lagrange Theory

Lagrange theory is often presented in textbooks in the following manner. There exists a Lagrangian function:

$$L(v,x,t) \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{such that } \text{Variation Integral } dt L = 0 \rightarrow F = dp/dt \quad ((2))$$

This yields an alternative approach to finding $F=dp/dt$ which seems to focus on a variation of paths. Lagrangian theory was developed for non-relativistic physics and

$$L = KE - V \text{ often } ((3)) \text{ (nonrelativistically)}$$

We suggest that one try to obtain Lagrangian theory from special relativity.

Lagrangian Theory from Special Relativity

A particle with rest mass m_0 at rest at $x=0, t$, as seen from a frame moving with $-v$, has:

$$E(m_0,v) \quad p(m_0,c) \quad \text{and } x',t' \text{ such that } x'/t' = v \quad ((4))$$

One may consider the transformation matrix:

$$\begin{bmatrix} g(v) & vg(v) \\ vg(v) & g(v) \end{bmatrix} \quad ((5))$$

with $g(v)$ unknown. ((5)) applies to both $x,t \rightarrow x',t'$ and $mocc \rightarrow E, p$ if one assumes that $p=mv$. Here we let $c=1$.

It is possible to find $g(v)$ using the Lorentz invariant:

$$-E^2 + p \cdot p \, c^2 = -m^2 c^4 \quad ((6))$$

Here, however, we do not wish to use ((6)). Rather we wish to use Newton's second law:

$$F = dp/dt \quad ((7))$$

In such a case:

$$dE/dt = v \, dp/dt \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Work} = \int dx \, F = \int v \, dp \quad ((8))$$

Then,

$$dg/dt = v \{d(gv)\} \quad \text{or} \quad d \ln(g) = -d \ln(1-v^2) \quad \text{or} \quad g = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2} \quad ((9))$$

In other words, it is Newton's second law which may be said to solve for the explicit form of $g(v)$ and it is this explicit form which allows one to take the Lorentz invariant:

$$-Et + px \quad ((10))$$

$$\text{and write} \quad t(-E + pv) = t L(v, m_0) = t \sqrt{1-v^2} m_0 = Lt \quad ((11))$$

From this one sees that $dL/dv \text{ partial} = p \quad ((12))$.

Thus, ((11)) is the action $\int L \, dt$ and it is a Lorentz invariant for a free particle and $dL/dv \text{ partial} = p$.

The next step is to recover $F=dp/dt$ which was used to find $g(v)$ in the first place. One requires a d/dt to act on p and can also use:

$$F = -\text{grad} \, V \quad \text{for a conservative force} \quad ((13))$$

The key idea seems to be to find a way to allow for a d/dt acting on p . This can be done by introducing a variational approach $L(v+\delta v, x+\delta x)$ because $v=dx/dt$ and integration by parts allows for one to bring in $-d/dt$. The entire goal of the variation is simply to allow for integration by parts to allow for the $dL/dv \text{ partial}$ part linked with δv to bring over a d/dt

acting on dL/dv . It is, however, special relativity and the form of $g(v)$ (given by $F=dp/dt$) which allows one to write $dL/dv=p$ and then variation of δv allows for the use of d/dt .

As a result, one may develop a Lagrangian:

$$L = -m_0 \sqrt{1-vv/cc} - V(x) \quad ((14))$$

$$\text{This leads to: } d/dt \frac{dL}{dv} - \frac{dL}{dx} = 0 \quad ((15))$$

Basically, one begins with special relativity and $F=dp/dt$ and returns to $dp/dt = F$, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Lagrangian theory arose as an alternative computational approach to obtaining Newton's second law. It was originally based on nonrelativistic physics and introduced a function $L(x,v,t)$ such that $dL/dv \text{ partial} = p$ and variation $\int dt L = 0$, leading to $F=dp/dt$.

Here, we argue that one may obtain Lagrangian theory from special relativity. We suggest that the key feature is the function $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ which is present in special relativity and show that this explicit form follows from $F=dp/dt$ for a free particle (i.e. $F=0$). From this $g(v)$ form, we show that $-Et+px = \text{Lorentz invariant} = t(-E+px) = t\{-m_0 \sqrt{1-vv/cc}\}$ where $L = -m_0 \sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and $dL/dv \text{ partial} = p$. From this result, one may seek an approach which recreates $F=dp/dt$ (which yielded the form $g(v)$ in the first place). Given that dL/dv is linked with p and that one needs d/dt to act on p , one may introduce a variational approach which, through integration by parts, converts $dL/dv \text{ partial} \delta v$ to $-d/dt \frac{dL}{dv} \text{ partial} \delta x$ (as is well-known from nonrelativistic theory).